
Analyzing political-religious criminality during the Dollfuß-/Schuschnigg-Regime – A case study of LLM-assisted historical network research

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Abstract

Analyzing political-religious criminality during the Dollfuß-/Schuschnigg-Regime – A case study of LLM-assisted historical network research

In this talk I will present a case study, which integrates Large Language Models (LLMs) into historical network research. Analyzing the construction of political-religious criminality during the Dollfuß-/Schuschnigg Regime in Austria (1933-1938), I am utilizing LLMs within a multi-methodological research process to extract named entities from court records. Transforming unstructured data from verdicts into structured data, this allows me to construct historical legal networks of offenses and defendants, which model interdependencies of their socio-economical, gender, and political characteristics and sentence outcomes.

This case study is guided by two underlying research directives. On the historical level, I am investigating how political criminality was constructed at court for political partisans (mainly National Socialists, Social Democrats, and Communists) during the transformation of the Austrian democracy to an autocracy in 1933-1938. On a methodological level, this case study showcases how to improve the automatic identification and extraction of entities and information from court records with LLMs, in order to facilitate further computational analysis of historical court networks.

This study is based on political trials processed at the provincial courts (LGSt1 and LGSt2) of Vienna during the Dollfuß-/Schuschnigg-Regime (1933-1938). There, I focused on verdicts in trials containing at least one political-religious offense, in which different forms of deviancy or dissent from the state-sanctioned religion – Catholicism – was punishable by law and thus became a political offense (compare e.g., Hanisch (2005) 2012; Ebner 2013). These political-religious offenses entailed in the then-current penal code (Tlapek 1933): §122 on the crime of religious disturbance and blasphemy; §175a on theft of religious objects; §302 incitement for enmity against racial and religious groups, society or corporations; §303 on defamation or insult of legally recognized churches or religious groups; and §304 on illegal support or dissemination of religious groups. Furthermore, I restricted the database to contain only processes against named persons, excluding all judicial investigations against unknown to ensure meaningful results.

Based on these constraints for operationalization, I identified 197 unique cases in 1933-1938 containing a total of 266(1) judicial inquiries and actions against 232 unique defendants.

*Speaker

The total of 258 judicial inquiries and actions resulted in 154 individual first-instance verdicts against 143 unique defendants: 97 convictions (63% of total verdicts), 24 acquittals (15.6% of total verdicts), and for the remainder an effective abatement of actions in 33 cases (21.4% of total verdicts), when the associated offending printing works were prohibited but no further legal actions were taken against the defendants.

(1) The higher number of judicial inquiries/actions is a result of that within each unique case number, multiple inquiries/actions are possible against multiple defendants and (in many instances even) printing works associated to a case, which then can result in multiple, individual verdicts against persons and prints.

In a first step, I made these verdicts machine-readable through Optical Character Recognition based on the Print M1 model by Transcribus (Read-Coop 2023; Accuracy: 2.2% CER), which I then manually corrected to achieve a 100% gold standard transcription of all verdicts. This preparation allowed me to build a corpus of verdicts.

Utilizing the highly formalized nature of court records, I compared in an experimental set-up results and optimization strategies for the extraction of both named entities and further information within these with LLMs. In order to balance and adhere to considerations for ethical usage, efficiency, and sustainability following the principle of minimal computing for generative AI (compare also Oberbichler & Petz 2025), I opted for an as-small-as-possible model for information extraction and locally employed the Open-Weights(2) model Llama-3.1-8b (META) with nomic-embed-text-v1.5 (Nomic-AI) for embeddings.

(2) Initially marketed as Open Access” by META itself, this assessment has been reversed since META doesn’t allow access to the source code and training data of the Llama-family models, but control of its weights only (compare e.g., to the European Open Source AI Index n.d.).

This set-up allows me to identify differences in semantic wordings as well as highlighting patterns of which deviancy was considered (non-) acceptable dependent on political partisanship, gender, and social status (approximated through the recorded profession, and employment status) of defendants.

Finally, this allows me to model networks of co-occurring offenses and the socio-economic, gender, and political markers of defendants dependent on sentence outcomes. This sheds light on hidden dynamics in the prosecution of political-religious deviancy and constitutes a step further to fill the gap of the missing systematic analysis of penal practice during the Dollfuß-/Schuschnigg-Regime (compare to Reiter-Zatloukal 2013), while extending on my previous case study on configurations of convictions focusing on the consolidated phase of the regime in 1935 (Petz and Pfeffer 2021).

In this contribution, I will reflect on pitfalls of the presented approach when working with sensitive data such as court records. This entails considerations on the compliance to data privacy and data protection regulations (GDPR) on research data management and workflows with localized LLMs and servers, issues of transparency and reproducibility when working with Open-Access vs closed-access models, as well as the issue of reproducing inherent biases both through the models used (e.g., Dai et al 2024) and the source basis. In the context of court records, Schwerhoff (2011, p. 40) stressed their nature as ‘involuntary ego-documents’ of the defendants and simultaneous representation of the perspectives of the courts. I want to stress, too, how problematic and moralizing labels are amplified in the context of the political-religious offenses presented here. Finally, I will highlight the opportunities and limits of a legal network model in analyzing penal practice systematically.

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